

OPTIMUM DESIGN OF LAMINATED GRP MATERIALS

A. F. JOHNSON

National Physical Laboratory, England

Composite materials are often combined with other materials such as foamed plastics and metals in a component, or they themselves may consist of combinations of different types of fibre reinforcement. Thus the designer is faced with a 'materials design problem', that is the selection of the best combination of materials for a particular application. This may be the combination with least cost, or for more critical components, least weight. For many applications of GRP materials there is a need for design formulae and design charts which optimise materials selection for relatively simple geometries and loads. Some problems of this type are formulated in the paper and solutions are obtained using the method of Lagrange multipliers. Formulae are given for determining the optimum lamina thicknesses in symmetric three and five ply materials to give maximum flexural rigidity and flexural strength for least weight or cost. The results are illustrated by design charts which are particularly relevant to the design of GRP laminates with combinations of two reinforcement types. The design of compound circular bars for optimum torsional and flexural rigidity is also considered and it is found that the design chart for sandwich materials may also be used for this problem.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is increasingly common for composites structures to contain several material combinations. Thus glass fibre reinforced plastics (GRP) may be combined with a foamed plastics core or with carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) skins, and a GRP laminate may itself consist of different types of reinforcement such as woven rovings (WR) and chopped strand mat (CSM). These material combinations are being considered because each material or type of reinforcement has particular features which the designer wishes to exploit. The component may require the high stiffness of CFRP, the chemical resistance of a CSM/polyester barrier or the cheapness and low density of a balsa wood or foamed plastics core. In general there will be many material combinations which will meet a given set of design loads. An important problem facing the designer of composites structures is the 'materials design problem', that is the selection of the best combination of materials for a particular application. This will usually be the combination with least cost, or for more critical applications, least weight.

In the design of high performance structures for aerospace applications, these problems are being tackled by the development of computer programs relevant to complex loading situations (see, for example, [1] - [3].) For other industries, such as transport and chemical plant, there is also a need for relatively simple design formulae and design charts which optimise materials selection for simpler geometries and loads and give guidance to the designer of less critical structures in GRP and sandwich materials. These may be obtained using the methods described here in conjunction with idealised models of material mechanical properties. The resulting formulae enable the designer to make basic decisions about material selection. For example, they might indicate whether it is better to use two materials laminated together in a particular way, with a third material as a core, or either material used separately. Having decided on the materials design, it may then be necessary to use a more detailed analysis of the composite structure using, say, laminated plate theory [4]. However in many cases, particularly in GRP applications, the materials design analysis will enable the stiffness and strength of the chosen combination to be estimated with sufficient accuracy for use in conventional design calculations.

Several optimisation problems of this type are formulated in the paper and analytical solutions are derived using the method of Lagrange multipliers. In Sections 2 and 3 formulae are given for determining the optimum lamina thicknesses in symmetric three and five ply materials to give maximum flexural rigidity and flexural strength for least weight or least cost. The results are illustrated by design charts which are particularly relevant to the design of GRP laminates with combinations of two reinforcement types. In Section 4 the design of compound bars of circular cross-section for optimum torsional and flexural rigidity is also considered and it is found that the design chart for three-ply sandwich materials may also be used for this problem. Section 5 briefly describes the application of the design charts to the design of a combined WR/CSM reinforced polyester resin laminate.

2. DESIGN OF THREE-PLY LAMINATED COMPOSITES

Many composite components are based on a three-ply sandwich structure, eg GRP/balsa/GRP cladding panels, CFRP/GRP/CFRP hybrid beams for springs, and GRP laminates for use in boats, tanks and pipes often consist of mixtures of WR or uni-directional (UD) glass fibres and CSM plies. For many of these applications beams and plates are subjected to transverse flexural loading. As a model for the materials selection problem, we consider the flexural properties of the symmetric three-ply beam shown in Fig. 1. The beam has unit width, thickness h and consists of a central core of material 1 with thickness h_1 with skins of material 2, thickness h_2 . The materials have densities ρ_1 and ρ_2 and are assumed to be linearly elastic with longitudinal Young's moduli E_1 and E_2 , respectively. We consider the flexural properties of the beam when deformed out of the plane of the laminations by a bending moment M per unit width. The axis of the beam is assumed to be a symmetry axis for each material so that there is no coupling between

bending and torsion. In the subsequent analysis we use approximate expressions for the flexural stiffness and strength of the three-ply beam in which shear stresses and transverse stresses, resulting from the variation in Poisson's ratio between the two materials, are neglected. These assumptions have been found to give good

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of three-ply beam in flexure

approximations to the more detailed formulae obtained from laminate theory except when the core is very flexible in shear and provided the beam is sufficiently long (see, for example, [5]). Although we are considering a beam analysis, the results should also provide an adequate approximation to the flexural properties of sandwich panels.

The problem of the optimum design of sandwich beams and panels has been considered in the literature, but previous results are only relevant to sandwiches with thin skins or soft cores. Thus in [5] and [6] attention is given to the optimum core thickness when $E_1 = 0$ and $h_2 \ll h_1$. Williams [7] considers a more general formulation, but in order to obtain specific solutions restricts himself to the case $E_1 \ll E_2$. Whilst these approximations are valid for certain lightweight sandwich panels, they are not relevant to the design of GRP laminates containing, say, WR and CSM reinforcements. For this reason we re-examine the problem here and seek solutions valid for all skin thicknesses and any E_1/E_2 ratio.

2.1 Design for flexural stiffness

With the assumptions given above, the flexural rigidity of the symmetric three-ply beam of unit width shown in Fig. 1 is given from classical beam theory as $D = E_1 I_1 + 2E_2 I_2$, where I_1 and I_2 are the moments of inertia of the cross-sections of plies 1 and 2 about the central horizontal axis of the beam cross-section. On expressing I_1 and I_2 in terms of the section geometry, we obtain

$$D = \frac{1}{12} [E_1 h_1^3 + E_2 (2h_2^3 + 6h_2 (h_1 + h_2)^2)] \quad (1)$$

Let w be the weight per unit area (in the plane of the laminations) of the three-ply material, then

$$w = \rho_1 h_1 + 2\rho_2 h_2$$

The optimum design problem is to choose ply thicknesses h_1 and h_2 so as to minimise the weight of the beam for a given flexural rigidity D . This is equivalent

mathematically to the dual problem of maximising D for a given weight w . The solution obtained here can be applied to both these problems, although in what follows we shall mainly be concerned with the minimum weight formulation. Alternatively ρ_1 and ρ_2 may be taken as the costs per unit volume of materials 1 and 2, w the cost of the laminate per unit area, and the optimum design problem is then to choose values of h_1 and h_2 which give the required flexural rigidity at lowest cost.

The algebraic details are considerably simplified with the correct choice of independent variables. We therefore introduce the total thickness h and the core thickness ratio v defined by

$$h = h_1 + 2h_2, \quad v = h_1/h. \quad (3)$$

After some algebraic manipulation the optimum design problem may be expressed in an alternative form. Find values of h and v which minimise

$$w = h [\rho_1 v + \rho_2 (1 - v)] \quad (4)$$

subject to the constraint

$$D = \frac{1}{12} h^3 [E_1 v^3 + E_2 (1 - v^3)], \quad (5)$$

where D is a given constant. Equations (4) and (5) define a constrained minimisation problem which may be solved mathematically using the method of Lagrange multipliers, (see, for example, [8]). Here we have two independent variables h, v , and a single constraint (5). On introducing the Lagrange multiplier λ , the solution is given by those values of h, v which minimise the function

$$L = h[\rho_1 v + \rho_2 (1 - v)] + \lambda [D - \frac{1}{12} h^3 (E_1 v^3 + E_2 (1 - v^3))]. \quad (6)$$

The minima of L occur at the stationary points where

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial h} = \frac{\partial L}{\partial v} = 0,$$

and differentiation of Eq. (6) yields the algebraic equations

$$\rho_1 v + \rho_2 (1 - v) - \frac{1}{4} \lambda h^2 [E_1 v^3 + E_2 (1 - v^3)] = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$h(\rho_1 - \rho_2) - \frac{1}{4} \lambda h^2 v^2 (E_1 - E_2) = 0.$$

Eq. (7) and (5) provide three equations for the determination of h, v and λ . The parameter λ is not required explicitly and may be eliminated from Eq. (7), which after some further algebra may be solved for v , giving

$$v = \left[\frac{(\rho_2 - \rho_1) E_2}{\rho_2 (E_2 - E_1)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (8)$$

With v defined by Eq. (8), the thickness h is given by Eq. (5) in terms of D , which is assumed to be known.

We must now consider whether the values of h and v defined here refer to a real minimum of w . It follows from Eq. (8) that v is real provided the pairs of inequalities $\rho_1 < \rho_2$ and $E_1 < E_2$ or $\rho_2 < \rho_1$, and $E_2 < E_1$ are satisfied. By examining the minimality condition [8], which is an expression involving second derivatives of L , it can be shown that Eq. (8) defines a minimum of w provided

Fig. 2 Design chart showing optimum core thickness h_1/h ($= v$) for three-ply beams under flexural loading.

$E_1 < E_2$. Since v is the core thickness ratio we also require that $0 < v < 1$ and it can be shown that this condition is satisfied when

$$E_1/\rho_1 < E_2/\rho_2. \quad (9)$$

We conclude that Eq. (8) defines the core thickness ratio for a minimum weight three-ply beam provided that $\rho_1 < \rho_2$, $E_1 < E_2$ and Eq. (9) are satisfied. Thus the mathematics confirms the intuitively obvious fact that the optimum design for a sandwich beam must have the heavier, stiffer material in the skins. Eq. (9) shows, in addition, that if the specific stiffness of the core is greater than that of the skins then the minimum weight design consists of the core material alone.

The design of the optimum three-ply laminate may now be summarised. First, check that the properties of the skin and core materials satisfy the inequalities given above. Calculate the core/sandwich thickness ratio v from Eq. (8). If the minimum weight design is required for a given flexural rigidity D , use these values of D and v in Eq. (5) and solve for the required thickness h . Alternatively; if the maximum flexural rigidity is required for a given weight w , use the values of v and w in Eq. (4) to solve for the thickness h . In this latter case we are making use of the duality of these two optimisation problems. As a design aid, we show in Fig. 2 a design chart for v calculated from Eq. (8). The continuous lines on the figure give the optimum core thickness ratio $v = h_1/h$ for several values of ρ_1/ρ_2 , as a function of E_1/E_2 , in the case when flexural rigidity is the design constraint.

2.2 Design for flexural strength

In this Section we consider the optimum design of three-ply laminates when the design constraint is flexural strength rather than flexural rigidity. Plastics composites such as GRP generally have low stiffness and moderate strength values, thus design is usually stiffness limited. However, in more critical applications, where a failure criterion such as resin cracking stress rather than the rupture stress is used, strength limitations may become significant. When considering strength properties many different modes of failure are possible. For simplicity we shall assume here that the three-ply material fails in flexure when the maximum tensile strain, which is at the surface, reaches a critical strain value e_f . Depending on the application being considered, e_f could be the ultimate failure strain of the material or the strain associated with resin cracking or the first microdamage.

Using a simple strength of materials analysis and assuming that the ply materials are linearly elastic to failure, it can be shown [9] that the strain e at a distance z from the neutral axis of a laminated beam subjected to a bending moment M per unit width, is given by

$$e = Mz/D, \quad (10)$$

where for a three-ply beam D is again given by Eq. (5). The maximum bending moment which the beam can sustain occurs when the maximum strain in the beam at $z = h/2$ reaches the failure strain e_f . Thus the bending moment at failure M_f is given by

$$M_f = 2e_f D/h = \frac{1}{6} h^2 e_f [E_1 v^3 + E_2 (1 - v^3)]. \quad (11)$$

If the core material has a much lower failure strain than the skin material, failure may take place at the edge of the core where $z = h_1/2$. In this case Eq. (11) is modified to

$$M_f = \frac{h^2 e_f}{6v} [E_1 v^3 + E_2 (1 - v^3)], \quad (12)$$

where e_f now refers to the failure strain of the core material. For GRP materials the failure strain of different reinforcement types are very similar and failure will usually occur at the outer surface. Thus Eq. (11) is likely to be most relevant in practice and this is the only case considered in the subsequent analysis.

Following the method of solution used in Section 2.1, the three-ply material with least weight for a given flexural strength is given by the minimum of the function

$$L = h[\rho_1 v + \rho_2(1 - v)] + \lambda [M_F - \frac{1}{6} e_f h^2 (E_1 v^3 + E_2 (1-v)^3)],$$

where λ is a Lagrange multiplier. The equations $\partial L/\partial h = \partial L/\partial v = 0$, along with the constraint Eq. (11), give three equations for determining h, v and λ . On carrying out these differentiations and eliminating λ , we find that v satisfies the cubic equation

$$v^3 - \frac{3\rho_2 v^2}{(\rho_2 - \rho_1)} + \frac{2E_2}{(E_2 - E_1)} = 0. \quad (13)$$

In this case we are not able to obtain a simple explicit formula for v . Eq. (13) shows that v depends on the two parameters ρ_1/ρ_2 and E_1/E_2 , and the roots of the equation are readily obtained by numerical computation. We are only interested in the roots of Eq. (13) which satisfy the condition $0 < v < 1$ and it is found that there is at most one of these for values of ρ_1/ρ_2 and E_1/E_2 in the range $0 < \rho_1/\rho_2, E_1/E_2 < 1$. This value of v is shown by the family² of broken curves in Fig. 2, as a function of E_1/E_2 for several values of ρ_1/ρ_2 .

The optimum design for the beam is now given as follows. First determine the core thickness ratio from Fig. 2 and then use Eq. (11) to calculate the thickness h in terms of the assumed failure strain e_f and the maximum allowable bending moment M_F . Alternatively h can be determined from Eq. (4) if it is required to maximise M_F for a given weight w . In order to show that this procedure defines a minimum weight for the three-ply beam, it is necessary to use an inspection method based on some typical numerical values for the chosen root v .

3. DESIGN OF FIVE-PLY LAMINATED COMPOSITES

The results given above apply to sandwich materials consisting of stiff skins to carry most of the load with a central core of lower cost, lower density material. For many applications with GRP laminates these simple sandwich combinations require modification. The main reason is that the stiffer skin material, which may contain UD or WR reinforcement, usually has a low resin content and thus a poor resistance to water and chemical environments. It is increasingly common, therefore, to design GRP laminates with water or chemically resistant skins, which may consist of a low stiffness CSM/polyester material. Thus a typical GRP laminate may consist of five plies; a central core of plastics foam or CSM/polyester, two main load carrying plies of WR/polyester or UD glass fibres, which are then faced with protective plies of a less stiff material such as CSM/polyester. In order to provide design information for this type of material combination, we consider here the optimum design of a symmetric five-ply laminated beam for flexural loading, in the particular case when the outer plies are a low stiffness material.

3.1 Design for flexural stiffness

We consider a symmetric five-ply beam which consists of the three-ply beam shown in Fig. 1 with an additional outer ply on each face of thickness h_3 , density ρ_3 and Young's modulus E_3 . With the same assumptions as in Section 2, the flexural rigidity of this compound beam is given by $D = E_1 I_1 + 2E_2 I_2 + 2E_3 I_3$, where I_3 is the moment of inertia of the cross-section of ply 3 about the central axis of the beam cross-section. It follows that

$$D = \frac{1}{12} [E_1 h_1^3 + E_2 (2h_2^3 + 6h_2(h_1 + h_2)^2) + E_3 (2h_3^3 + 6h_3(h_1 + 2h_2 + h_3)^2)] \quad (14)$$

and the weight per unit surface area of the laminate is given by

$$w = \rho_1 h_1 + 2\rho_2 h_2 + 2\rho_3 h_3. \quad (15)$$

The optimum design problem is to choose h_1 , h_2 and h_3 so as to minimise w for a given value of flexural rigidity D . We can simplify the algebra considerably by the correct choice of independent variable. Let

$$v = h_1/h, \quad u = (h_1 + 2h_2)/h, \quad (16)$$

where $h = h_1 + 2h_2 + 2h_3$ is the total thickness, then it follows that

$$h_2/h = \frac{1}{2}(u - v), \quad h_3/h = \frac{1}{2}(1 - u). \quad (17)$$

In terms of the variables h , u , v it can be shown that

$$w = h [\rho_1 v + \rho_2(u - v) + \rho_3(1 - u)], \quad (18)$$

$$D = \frac{1}{12} h^3 [E_1 v^3 + E_2(u^3 - v^3) + E_3(1 - u^3)].$$

Eq. (18) can be used as a basis for determining the optimum design of a five-ply laminate. The analysis of Section 2.1 has indicated that if the specific stiffness of ply 3 is less than the average for plies 1 and 2, then a minimum weight design is not possible unless $h_3 = 0$. Since we are interested in the case when ply 3 has a low specific stiffness, we consider the case when the designer specifies the proportion of the laminate taken up by the protective surface plies and then wishes to optimise the thickness of the core and the main load bearing plies 2. We therefore assume that h_3/h is given and hence by Eq. (17) u is known. We then consider the problem of determining thickness h and core thickness ratio v so as to minimise w for a fixed u and D subject to the constraint (18)₂.

Using the Lagrange multiplier method, this is given by the minimum value of the function

$$L = h [\rho_1 v + \rho_2(u - v) + \rho_3(1 - u)] + \lambda [D - \frac{1}{12} h^3 (E_1 v^3 + E_2(u^3 - v^3) + E_3(1 - u^3))], \quad (19)$$

where λ is a Lagrange multiplier. On eliminating λ from the conditions for a minimum, $\partial L/\partial h = \partial L/\partial v = 0$, it can be shown that v is given by

$$v = \left[\frac{(\rho_2 - \rho_1) [E_3 + u^3(E_2 - E_3)]}{(E_2 - E_1) [\rho_3 + u(\rho_2 - \rho_3)]} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}}. \quad (20)$$

This is the modified form of Eq. (8) for the five-ply material and it can be verified that as $h_3 \rightarrow 0$ (ie $u \rightarrow 1$) Eq. (20) reduces to Eq. (8). It follows from the earlier analysis that the value of v given here corresponds to a minimum of w . With v defined by Eq. (20) the thickness h for a given flexural rigidity D and skin thickness parameter u is given by solving Eq. (18) for h .

In order to examine how the outer protective plies modify the design of the central load bearing sandwich, it is necessary to plot Eq. (20) on design charts for values of u , E_1/E_2 , etc. of interest. This is illustrated in Fig. 3 by a design chart for the case $u = 0.8$, which corresponds to a five-ply laminate with skin thicknesses $h_3/h = 0.1$. To reduce further the number of parameters we consider the situation when materials 1 and 3 are the same. Thus we take $E_3 = E_1$, $\rho_3 = \rho_1$ and note that v now depends on two parameters ρ_1/ρ_2 and E_1/E_2 . This simplified situation is relevant to the design of GRP laminates containing a core and skins of one material, such as CSM/polyester, with intermediate load bearing plies of another material such as WR/polyester. The continuous lines in Fig. 3 give the optimum core thickness ratio h_1/h for the flexural stiffness limited beam in the case when $h_3/h = 0.1$. We note from Eq. (17) that for $h_2 > 0$, $v < u$, and when the design

Fig. 3 Design chart showing optimum core thickness h_1/h ($= v$) for five-ply beams under flexural loading. Material 3 is the same as material 1 and $h_3/h = 0.1$ (ie $u = 0.8$).

curves in Fig. 3 reach the value $v = 0.8$, the lowest weight design consists of material 1 alone.

3.2 Design for flexural strength

We again consider the simplest case when failure occurs at an outside face of the beam. Following the analysis of Section 2.2, when the strain in the beam reaches the failure strain e_f , the critical bending moment M_f is given by

$$M_f = \frac{1}{6} e_f h^2 [E_1 v^3 + E_2 (u^3 - v^3) + E_3 (1 - u^3)] . \quad (21)$$

If we restrict attention to the case when u is fixed, then we require the values of v and h which minimise w subject to the constraint (21), where M_f and e_f are assumed to be given. Using the methods of analysis described above, we find that the condition for a minimum weight design is that v should be a root of the cubic equation

$$v^3 - \frac{3v^2 [\rho_3 + (\rho_2 - \rho_3)u]}{(\rho_2 - \rho_1)} + \frac{2 [E_3 + u^3(E_2 - E_3)]}{(E_2 - E_1)} = 0 . \quad (22)$$

The roots of this cubic have been examined numerically and the root which satisfies the condition $0 < v < u < 1$ is shown by the family of broken curves in Fig. 3. This design chart was again prepared for the special case when $h_3/h = 0.1$ (ie $u = 0.8$) and when materials 1 and 3 are assumed to be the same. Since Eq. (22) reduces to Eq. (13) in the special case $h_3 = 0$ (ie $u = 1$), it follows that the chosen root of (22) also corresponds to a minimum weight design. Having determined $h_1/h (= v)$ from the design chart, the laminate thickness h may be determined from Eq. (21) for a minimum weight design or from Eq. (18)₁ for a maximum strength design.

4. DESIGN OF COMPOUND BARS

In this Section we consider the minimum weight design for both torsional and flexural stiffness of compound bars of circular cross-section with a central circular core and composed of two materials. These problems are relevant to the application of composite materials to components such as drive shafts, lighting poles, shafts for sports goods etc. which lend themselves to fabrication by pultrusion and by overwrapping or filament winding a central unreinforced core. The main reason for including these problems here is that it will be shown that the optimum design is controlled by the design chart Fig. 2 derived for three-ply laminates. For brevity we consider only design for stiffness, although the modifications needed to include strength properties can be made for particular failure modes of interest.

4.1 Design for torsion

We consider the compound circular bar shown in Fig. 4 which is assumed to be twisted through an angle α by application of a torque T about the central axis. The bar has length l , radius r and consists of a core of material 1 with radius r_1 surrounded by a cylindrical skin of material 2. It is assumed that the bar axis is a symmetry axis of each material so that there is no coupling between bending and torsion. The longitudinal shear moduli of the core and skin materials are G_1 and G_2 respectively. With the assumptions of the Saint-Venant theory of torsion (see, for example, [10]), the torsional rigidity of the compound bar, Tl/α , is given by

$$Tl/\alpha = \frac{1}{2} \pi [G_1 r_1^4 + G_2 (r^4 - r_1^4)] . \quad (23)$$

If ρ_1 and ρ_2 are the densities (or costs per unit volume) of materials 1 and 2, then the total weight (cost) per unit length w is given by

$$w = \pi \rho_1 r_1^2 + \pi \rho_2 (r^2 - r_1^2) . \quad (24)$$

Fig. 4 Schematic diagram of compound bar

We require the values of r_1 and r which minimise the weight w for a given torsional rigidity. Introducing as a new variable the core thickness ratio v , defined by

$$v = r_1/r, \quad (25)$$

we require the values of v and r which minimise the function

$$L = \pi r^2 [\rho_1 v^2 + \rho_2(1 - v^2)] + \lambda [Tl/\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\pi r^4(G_1 v^4 + G_2(1 - v^4))], \quad (26)$$

where λ is a Lagrange multiplier. On forming the two equations, $\partial L/\partial r = \partial L/\partial v = 0$ and eliminating λ , we find after some algebra that v is given by

$$v = \left[\frac{(\rho_2 - \rho_1)G_2}{\rho_2(G_2 - G_1)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (27)$$

On examining the second derivatives of L , it can be shown that the value of v defined in Eq. (27) corresponds to a minimum of w . Having determined $v (= r_1/r)$ from Eq. (27) we must solve Eq. (23) for r in terms of v and the required torsional rigidity Tl/α . This is the solution to the minimum weight design problem. Alternatively, r can be determined from Eq. (24) in terms of a given weight w and these values of r and v will then maximise Tl/α for that given weight.

Comparison of Eq. (8) and (27) shows that the optimum core thickness ratio for a compound bar in torsion satisfies the same equation as the core thickness ratio of a three-ply beam in flexure, provided G_1 and G_2 are used instead of E_1 and E_2 . It follows that the design chart in Fig. 2 is directly applicable to the design of a compound circular bar for optimum torsional rigidity, with h_1/h replaced by r_1/r and E_1/E_2 replaced by G_1/G_2 .

4.2 Design for flexure

We consider here the flexural rigidity of the compound bar shown in Fig. 4 which is assumed to be bent by bending moments M acting perpendicular to the bar axis. The analysis is based on an approximate expression for the flexural rigidity D obtained from elementary beam theory. Thus we assume that $D = E_1 I_1 + E_2 I_2$, where I_1 and I_2 are the moments of inertia of the core and skin sections about the central axis of the beam cross-section and E_1, E_2 their respective longitudinal Young's moduli. It follows that

$$D = \frac{1}{4} \pi r^4 [E_1 v^4 + E_2 (1 - v^4)], \quad (28)$$

where v is again given by Eq. (25). This expression for the flexural rigidity of a compound bar is derived on the assumption that during flexure the only non-zero stresses are longitudinal tension or compression and that shear stresses or through thickness stresses, arising from the variation in Poisson's ratio between the materials, may be neglected. Comparison of Eq. (28) and (23) shows that the flexural rigidity D has the same form of dependence on r and v as the torsional rigidity Tl/a , provided that G_1, G_2 are replaced by E_1, E_2 and the multiplicative constant is changed from $\pi/2$ to $\pi/4$. It follows that the optimum core thickness of a compound bar for least weight is given by Eq. (27), with G_1, G_2 replaced by E_1, E_2 , or by the three-ply beam relation (8), with h_1/h replaced by r_1/r . The design chart Fig. 2 may thus be used for optimising the flexural properties of a compound circular bar.

5. DESIGN EXAMPLE

The use of the design charts is illustrated here by considering the materials design problem for a GRP laminate containing CSM and WR reinforcement, and subjected to flexural loading. Johnson [9] has reviewed the properties of these materials and typical values of flexural Young's modulus and density for CSM/polyester and WR/polyester materials are:

Material	Density 10^3 kg/m^3	Modulus GPa
CSM/polyester	1.4	6.0
WR/polyester	1.75	13.5

The Young's modulus value for the orthotropic WR/polyester material refers to a weave direction, which is assumed to lie along the beam. The CSM/polyester material is assumed to be isotropic in the laminate plane. We wish to consider (a) a stiffness limited design for a required flexural rigidity per metre width $D = 300 \text{ Nm}$, and (b) a strength limited design for an ultimate bending moment per metre width $M_F = 200 \text{ N}$. The failure criterion for the strength calculation is that the maximum allowable strain is $e_F = 0.002$, which is a typical strain value corresponding to the onset of first irreversible damage in these materials (see [9]). We are interested in evaluating four possible configurations of these two types of glass fibre reinforcement. These are: all CSM, all WR, the least weight WR/CSM/WR sandwich material and the least weight CSM/WR/CSM/WR/CSM laminate, in which each of the outer CSM reinforced skins takes up 10% of the total thickness.

With the notation of Sections 2 and 3, materials 1 and 3 are CSM/polyester and material 2 is WR/polyester. From the data given here $\rho_1/\rho_2 = 0.8$ and $E_1/E_2 = 0.44$. Calculated values of flexural rigidity D , maximum bending moment M_F , thickness h , core thickness ratio $v = h_1/h$ and laminate weight per unit area w are given in Table 1 for the four types of reinforcement, using the materials data above. Standard beam bending formulae were used for calculating the properties of the single

ply constructions. For the three-ply WR/CSM/WR laminate values of v were read from Fig. 2 with $\rho_1/\rho_2 = 0.8$ and $E_1/E_2 = 0.44$ for both the stiffness and strength limited cases. In the former case the thickness $h = 6.7$ mm was then obtained by solving Eq. (5) for h with $v = 0.6$ and $D = 300$ Nm. The weight w was then obtained from Eq. (4) and the maximum bending moment for this laminate given by Eq. (12). The remainder of the table was completed in a similar manner. Fig. 3 was used to determine the optimum value of v for the five-ply laminate with $u = 0.8$ ($h_3/h = 0.1$).

Table 1 shows that the least weight design for the required flexural rigidity of $D = 300$ Nm is the WR/CSM/WR laminate, with thickness 6.7 mm and core thickness $h_1 = 0.6h = 4$ mm. The CSM and WR constructions are 15% and 9% heavier for the same stiffness. If the laminate is to have CSM/polyester skins for environmental protection, then the optimum arrangement (for the case when $h_3/h = 0.1$) consists of a 7.4 mm laminate with CSM/polyester core, thickness $h_2 = 0.52 h = 3.8$ mm, and skins thickness 0.7 mm, with two WR plies of thickness 1.1 mm each. Its weight is about 8% above the minimum weight WR/CSM/WR laminate. Similar remarks can be made about the flexural strength limited design where, once again, the WR/CSM/WR laminate has the lowest weight. It may not always be possible to fabricate this optimum GRP laminate, however the theory does define the laminate structure which the fabricator should be aiming for. We note that for these materials $\rho_1/\rho_2 = 0.8$, hence the weight saving at the optimum laminate design is not very great. This will become much more significant for combinations of materials with greater variation in density.

Design criteria	Reinforcement type	D (Nm)	M_F (N)	h (mm)	v	w (kg/m ²)
Stiffness limited, by flexural rigidity D = 300 Nm	CSM	300	140	8.4	-	11.8
	WR	300	184	6.4	-	11.2
	WR/CSM/WR	300	178	6.7	0.6	10.3
	CSM/WR/CSM/WR/CSM	300	160	7.4	0.52	11.1
Strength limited, by ultimate bending moment $M_F = 200$ N at 0.2% failure strain.	CSM	500	200	10	-	14
	WR	332	200	6.7	-	11.7
	WR/CSM/WR	352	200	7.1	0.5	11.2
	CSM/WR/CSM/WR/CSM	409	200	8.1	0.43	12.4

Table 1 Calculated properties of GRP laminates, with a comparison of least weight three-ply, five-ply ($h_3/h = 0.1$), all CSM and all WR constructions. (D and M_F are the flexural rigidity and maximum bending moment / m width and w is the laminate weight / m²)

6. CONCLUSIONS

We have shown that elementary mathematical analysis can lead to design formulae for optimising the properties of certain composite structures containing more than one material or type of reinforcement. These formulae and design charts provide a strategy for tackling the 'materials design problem', by indicating the optimum thicknesses of each material in laminates and compound bars.

Now that composite materials are being used increasingly in medium technology applications, there is a need for many more design formulae of the type presented here, which give the designer insight into the best way of using the available materials. The emphasis in the paper has been on simple examples which illustrate the mathematical methods needed for these constrained optimisation problems. There are many other materials design problems which can be formulated in the same way and in future work it is hoped to apply these methods to the optimum design of filament wound pipes and compound bars.

REFERENCES

- 1 TETLOW, R. Structural engineering design and applications. Chapter 4 in Carbon fibres in engineering (ed. M. LANGLEY) 1973, McGraw-Hill, London.
- 2 BERT, C.W. and CHEN, T.L.C., Optimal design of composite material plates to resist buckling under biaxial compression. Trans. Japan Soc. for Composite Materials 2, 1976, pp 7-10.
- 3 BERT, C.W. Optimal design of a composite material plate to maximise its fundamental frequency. J. Sound and Vibration 50, 1977, pp 229-237.
- 4 ASHTON, J.E., HALPIN, J.C. and PETIT, P.H., Primer on composite materials analysis. 1969, Technomic, Stamford.
- 5 ALLEN, H.G. Analysis and design of structural sandwich panels. 1969, Pergamon, London.
- 6 KUENZI, E.W. Minimum weight structural sandwich. US Forest Service Res. Note. 1965, FPL - 086.
- 7 WILLIAMS, J.G. Stress analysis of polymers, 1973, Longman, London.
- 8 GUE, R.L. and THOMAS, M.E. Mathematical methods in operations research. 1968, Macmillan, New York.
- 9 JOHNSON, A.F. Engineering design properties of GRP. 1978, British Plastics Federation, London.
- 10 SOKOLNIKOFF, I.S. Mathematical theory of elasticity. 1951, McGraw-Hill, New York.